

DRL for VNF placement in Inter-Data Center Elastic Optical Networks

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Abstract: A novel DRL solution for service provisioning over a cloud/EON stratum is presented. The benefit of DRL is that it can be adopted in different (unseen) EON topologies attaining better service blocking compared to traditional heuristics. © 2023 The Author(s)

1. Introduction

Network Function Virtualization (NFV) and Software Defined Networking (SDN) enable agile and flexible provisioning of network services for vertical industries (e.g., Industry 4.0, eHealth, automotive). To fulfill the diverse and strict requirements of each vertical service, tailored virtual networks, called *network slices*, are deployed. A network slice consists of several Virtual Network Functions (VNF) distributed geographically in different Data Centers (DCs). The high bandwidth and spectral efficiency of Elastic Optical Networks (EONs) make them one of the most promising technologies for DC interconnection. EON can achieve efficient use of the optical spectrum by allocating just enough spectrum resources with a granularity of 6.25 GHz to support diverse bandwidth demands such as 10, 40, 100, 400 Gb/s. The automatic provisioning of network services over an inter-DC EON is challenging since it entails deciding: (1) the placement of the VNFs in the DCs; and (2) the setting up of lightpaths interconnecting those DCs applying a routing and spectrum assignment (RSA) algorithm. Additionally, all the lightpaths are subject to meet the spectrum continuity and contiguity constraints, which does increase the overall complexity of the network service provisioning. Network services are modeled as a Service Function Chain (SFC) or a VNF Forwarding Graph (VNF-FG). SFCs represent a linear sequence of VNFs where the traffic is forwarded in a predefined order. On the other hand, VNF-FGs describe meshed VNF interconnections tackling more realistic network service deployments. Both SFC and VNF-FG placement are known to be NP-hard problems [1].

Most of the existing works in the literature address the VNF placement problem by using optimization problem-solving (typically formulated as Integer Linear Programming) or heuristics [2, 3]. Recently, Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) techniques have been applied to address decision-making problems, including the VNF placement. DRL learns from direct interaction with the system environments, i.e., it does not require initial data for training. In contrast to optimization problem-solving, DRL achieves better scalability upon both large cloud/network infrastructure and high dynamic service behavior since it can handle high dimensional data. In addition, DRL can capture the dynamic behavior of the system, as it adapts its decisions to the current state of the environment, unlike heuristics that adopt a fixed scheme focused on immediate performance.

Herein, we evaluate the performance of a novel DRL-based solution for the autonomous provisioning of network services over distributed DCs interconnected by an EON. The solution relies on two cooperating DRL agents that efficiently choose the DCs to host the VNFs and the lightpaths interconnecting them. We developed a VNF placement environment compatible with OpenAIGym to train the DRL agent using *invalid action masking* technique. The generalization capability and *continual learning* is evaluated by applying a policy learned in one network topology to a different topology. We compare the performance of the proposed solution against a heuristic algorithm in terms of service blocking rate.

2. System Model

The substrate EON is modeled as a directed graph $G(N, L)$. N is a set of optical switching nodes i.e., Reconfigurable Optical Add-Drop Multiplexers (ROADMs) which are attached to a DC. L is a set of optical links. The available computing, memory and storage resources on a DC are denoted as $C = \{C_{cpu}, C_{mem}, C_{hdd}\}$. Similarly, each link $l(u, v) \in L$ interconnecting a pair of optical nodes $u, v \in N$ has F available frequency slots (FSs) and a communication latency determined by D . Likewise, a network service request is modeled as a VNF-FG i.e., a directed graph $G_V(N_V, L_V)$. N_V represents a set of interconnected VNFs with a demand of resources denoted by $R = \{R_{cpu}, R_{mem}, R_{hdd}\}$. L_V represents the virtual links between VNFs with a bandwidth demand F_V in terms of FSs and a latency requirement of D_V . The lightpath supporting a virtual link is denoted as $P(L_V) = \{l_1, \dots, l_n\}; l_n \in L$. This lightpath is the substrate optical path interconnecting a pair of DCs.

When a service request is received from a pool of predefined service types, denoted by $NS = \{ns_1, \dots, ns_{|NS|}\}$, a placement algorithm selects the DC and optical resources that do fulfill the service requirements (i.e., computing,

spectrum and latency). Such a placement algorithm makes its decision according to the current state of the available resources typically reported by compute (e.g., aggregated amount of unused CPU, memory and storage) and network (e.g., number and position of unused FSs) controllers. The output of the placement algorithm describes: i) the set of DCs to host the VNFs, and ii) the lightpaths interconnecting those selected DC. The service is blocked if either compute resources or networking requirements cannot be met.

3. Proposed DRL-based Approach

Our DRL-based solution is designed to manage the deployment of network services in realistic scenarios, where service requests have stochastic arrival and departure and are represented as complex meshed VNF-FGs. As mentioned earlier, our solution consists of two agents. One of them computes the lightpaths between a pair of DCs. The computed lightpaths must not only fulfill the requirements of the service virtual links (i.e., the number of unused FSs F_V and maximum latency D_V) but also the spectrum continuity and contiguity constraints imposed by EON technology. We presented this agent in [4]. On the other hand, the second agent makes the selection of a suitable DC to host the VNF. That is, a DC with sufficient unused resources to allocate a VNF, $C > R$. Then, for each service request, the second agent tries to place every VNF $n_V \in N_V$ into a candidate DC. The neural network of the agent takes as *input state* the available computing resources C in every DC and the latency of the best lightpaths $P(L_V)$ interconnecting every pair of DCs reported by the first agent. The input state is complemented by the VNF requirements consisting of: (1) the resource demand vector R of the VNF n_V ; and (2) the bandwidth F_V and latency D_V needs of the virtual links l_V . The output of the neural network or *actionspace* corresponds to the selected DCs for the VNF placement. For every successful VNF allocation, the agent will receive a *reward* of 0. If the whole network service (i.e., VNF-FG) is deployed, the reward is equal to the aggregate compute capacity (i.e., CPU, memory, and storage) successfully allocated. This favors the deployment of complete network services. Otherwise, the reward will be negative when a VNF cannot be deployed since either constraints or requirements cannot be met. Figure 1 (a) depicts the scheme of the proposed DRL-based solution.

Fig. 1. (a) DRL-based solution, (b) NSFNet topology and (c) Unseen network topology.

4. Performance Evaluation

For the training phase, we developed a customized environment compatible with OpenAI Gym to tackle the VNF placement problem over an EON and leverage state-of-the-art RL implementations, such as Stable Baseline 3. Details of the agent that computes the lightpaths are given in [4]. The agent responsible for the DC selection was implemented using the Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) algorithm with invalid action masking. The PPO is a policy gradient method for reinforcement learning which is simpler to implement and attains better performance than other state-of-the-art approaches. Invalid action masking is a technique that avoids repeatedly generating invalid actions by removing them from the action space. In our environment, all DCs without enough computational capacity to host a VNF are removed from the action space with invalid action masking. The agent was implemented with the following parameters: a learning rate of 10^{-5} , a discount factor of 0.95, a batch size of 256 and five fully connected hidden layers with 128 neurons in the neural network.

To study the generalization capability of the proposed DRL solution, training was first carried out using the NSFNet topology consisting of 14 optical nodes and 42 fiber links as shown in Fig. 1 (b). Once the DRL training is complete, the trained model was used to perform online service provisioning in an unseen network topology with 14 nodes and 22 links as shown in Fig. 1 (c). In both topologies, each ROADM node is attached to a DC with a total CPU capacity of 100 cores. Each optical link can accommodate 100 FSs. We defined three different network service types with 2, 4 or 6 VNFs; 2, 10 or 20 virtual links; requiring a bandwidth of 2, 4 or 6 FSs and a maximum delay of 5, 10 or 15 ms. The CPU demand of each VNF is evenly distributed among [1, 5, 10]. The provisioning of 5,000 service requests was executed to evaluate the performance of our solution using the service blocking rate metric. This describes the number of blocked out of the total requested network services. Figure 2 (a) plots the service blocking rate for our solution and a heuristic algorithm for the two aforementioned topologies. The heuristic benchmark algorithm selects the DC with higher residual computing resources as long as the latency and bandwidth requirements are met. The algorithm computes the lightpaths with k-shortest path algorithm.

Fig. 2. Network Service (NS) Blocking Rate and Training for (a) NSFNet and (b) Unseen topology

From the experimental results, we observe that our DRL-based solution enhances the performance (i.e., lower blocking) than the heuristic algorithm for both NSFNet (used in training) and the topology not considered/seen during the training. Observe that, the higher the service load is, the more performance improvement is attained achieved by our proposed solution. Concerning the generalization capability, Fig 2 (a) shows that the performance of our agent using the unseen topology is still better than the heuristic despite being an unknown topology for the agent. For instance, under a traffic load of 50 Erlangs, our solution does reduce the service blocking by roughly 20%. Although the model performs well in the unseen topology, the knowledge acquired during the training can be used to adapt it to changes in the topology. We used the trained model to learn in the unseen topology. This is known as *continuous learning*. Fig. 2 (b) shows how using a previously trained model leads to accelerate the convergence in training on a new environment. Such a convergence is reduced from 2.2 to 0.8 million training episodes. It is also observed that good reward results are obtained since early training episodes.

5. Conclusions

This paper addresses the VFN placement over data centers interconnected by an EON by leveraging a DRL-based solution. Experimental results demonstrate that the proposed solution is able to generalize over different topologies and can adapt quickly to changes in topologies. Our solution effectively attains a better service blocking compared to a baseline heuristic algorithm by combining different techniques such as cooperating agents, invalid action masking and continual learning.

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